

An Overview of Femininity in Indian Public Health Sector

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Abstract

A comprehensive amount of femininity existed and practiced in the public health sector of India. In fact, National Rural Health Mission enabled an enhanced engaged of women in number, making the public health sector one of the sectors that employed women in large numbers.

Aims: The chief aim of this paper was to examine the amount, approach, and consequences of women's engagement in the public health sector and to identify the factors mutually conducive for women and public health sector.

Setting and design: This paper being a part of the overall doctoral research by the author conducted during the year 2009-11 throughout the country.

Methods and materials: Research conducted mainly through qualitative form of research and data collected by employing several case studies, sample surveys, and interviews. Quite a few facts examined in the premises of literatures such as "Rural Health Survey 2009", "MIS on NRHM 2011", "Framework of Implementation of NRHM 2005", "Bulletins of Sample Registration System 2006, 2008", "National Family Health Survey 2006, 2008" and "District Level Household Survey 2006, 2008".

Results: Almost two million women were employed or engaged in the public health sector of India as of 2012. However, their number was expected to increase further because still the public health centres were not adequately staffed and a range of staff was required as per the norms of the Indian Public Health Standards (IPHS). The situation has been described as "towards a numerical adequacy" or 'statistical control' for women in the public health sector of India. In fact, women were playing a key role in various public health programs such as immunization, institutional delivery, nutrition, awareness, hygiene, sanitation and other peripheral activities and promoted the slothful health indicators. Women health workforce in the rural areas utilized their money and time comparatively better than their counterparts in the urban areas. They promoted their households, other livelihoods, and reduced the overall burden of diseases.

Conclusion: Women have contributed significantly to improve the slow-moving health indicators of the country and there was optimistic spillover effects on other social- developmental sector evident.

Key words: Women Health Workers; Indian Public Health Sector; Numerical Adequacy of Women; Femininity

Introduction:

Public health sector in India is witnessing a tremendous amount of feminism because of the employment and voluntarism of a mark able number of female health workforce that has been ranged from Public Health Administrator, Specialists, Gynecologists, other Doctors, Auxiliary Nurse Midwives (ANM), Staff Nurse, Public Health Workers, and Volunteers in form of Accredited Social Health Workers (ASHA). The volume of women's participation and involvement in the Public Health Sector witnessed a marked increase since inception of the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) in the year 2005. The amount of femininity would further increase provided the number of health facilities get extended and adequately staffed to the tune of Indian Public Health Standard (IPHS). The increased role of women under NRHM could have varied reasons and consequences that have been studied and communicated by different scholars in different manners. In any case, the contribution of women to the public health sector has been credible.

Aims and objectives:

Gender justice, parity, and equality have become a matter of great relevance in neo sociology and it has enhanced the scope of various studies on gender issues across almost all sectors. One of the prime focus of gender studies usually started with equality of numbers of women and men, respectively employed or enrolled in the sector. The number of women does value in any organization, institution, and systems that may range from government departments, educational institutions, hospitals, and other public health organizations and institutions. Therefore, the purpose of this paper has been to present an overview of amount of femininity in the public health sector of India.

Statement of the problem

The suitability of the women workforce in some capacity has been a matter of special suitability for the health sector either public or private. Usually, a woman comes across two major problems due to poor public health care system. It hurts women not only economically however, mentally and psychologically also. A well developed and properly

structured public health centres in the proximity with a regular, qualitative, and cost effective service ultimately ease the burden of a woman in the household. Any decline in the burden of diseases, would make a woman more than happy and secure. Therefore, development of public health sector would be also required for gender justice and security. Secondly, by employing woman we can expect more sensitized health care services to the community. Women were also having natural concern for the proper care of their children and programs of nutrition, institutional delivery, immunization, and population control were most relevant to them. The emotion of not easily giving up provide them ample opportunities to manage any public health centre and maintaining public health preparedness. Different studies were done on gender issues in a different sector and there was a lack of appropriate information about femininity in the public health sector. The shortage of both qualitative and quantitative data on the amount and consequences of femininity in the public health sector was deeply felt. There has been problems in quantification of gender equality and parity in different sector as there were no any direct methods to quantify their contribution. There was diversified literatures and reports that were not integrated over gender issues. All those varied literatures and information were needed to be integrated and communicated properly. There was a tremendous lack of involvement of the academic fraternity in the public health related issues. It was needed to promote the involvement of the universities in the public health programs. More and more such kind of research and studies if conducted properly and communicated well, would certainly promote the implementation and evaluation of various public health programs which was still not adequate despite several internal and external arrangements.

Literature review:

The National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) has been one of the most reviewed programs in the country, vigorously reviewed not only internally however, externally. The Common Review Missions (CRMs) were an internal arrangement and a mechanism for evaluating the performance of the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) in different states. Several reports of the CRM were available in a periodical manner that also hinted about the amount women's contribution and activities in the public health sector of India (CRM Reports, 2007- 2012). The 'Framework of implementation of the NRHM' (MOHFW 2005) prescribing mandates for NRHM also suggested the tasks, action points, and timeline to achieve those action points. It clearly mentioned that women have to play key role in achieving the public health goals in the country. After a study it was reported that in India women since used to lend their households used to suffer more in case of any illness of family members due to burden of diseases. It has been also reported that women residing in the rural areas usually suffered more and faced the burden of diseases (Gill, S 2006). It was evident from the "MIS report 2010 or

Annual report 2010' that women were engaged in large numbers which could be validated through various Rural Health Surveys published in a periodical manner (RHS, 2007-2012).

According to *Dr. S. Hari*, "It would take at least further fifty years in India on current rate to adequately staff each public health facility in the country, including doctors and paramedics, as per norms of the Indian Public Health Standards" (Hari, S 2008). It was also evident that huge gap in the workforce persisted in the public health care system of the country. Therefore, the number of women was expected to increase further if all vacant positions get filled in the country. A norms for minimum number of medical and Para medical persons for each level of health care unit already prescribed under the norms of "Indian Public Health Standards. On this basis, the gap in human resources in the public health sector of the country could be easily identified. Women's role in managing immunization, institutional delivery, nutrition, hygiene, sanitation activities was quite impressive and their performance in capacity as ANMs, AWWs and ASHAs were extremely remarkable and laudable (Singh 2009).

Some surveys reported related to '*time use*' and '*money use*' pattern among the women had stated the distinction between the *urban* and *rural* women. The '*money use*' and '*time use*' pattern among women worker under NRHM significant, though it required a dedicated research despite results of other researchers in India on this issue could apply to current research also. It also further required to assess the achievements and contributions of women work force under the NRHM. Some surveys reported related to '*time use*' pattern among women work force in India available under the aegis of the *Central Statistical Organization* and Department of *Program Implementation and Statistics* to the Government of India.

'*Time use*' pattern is a method to ascertain the quality and quantity of time a woman usually used to provide their respective households and employment. In fact, any worker women expected to provide qualitative and quantitative time to both forms of labor such as household labor and employment related labor. Thus, they required to develop skills and capabilities to manage time accordingly. This phenomenon related to time management has been most often referred as '*time use*' pattern or '*labor force participation rate*' in most surveys. *Dr. Usha Kapadia* in a study has found that women turned into a better managers of their respective time in both urban and rural settings in comparison of their male counterparts (Kapadia 2008). Women public health workers were found to be contributing significantly to the households, livelihoods, and also the public health care centres where they worked. They worked as a key linkage between the community and public health care centre.

Some surveys related to '*money use*' pattern among the worker, women also exhibited different attitudes while

living in a respective urban and rural areas. Usually, women in rural areas utilized their money in respectively better and constructive manner with respect to their urban counterparts. Women in rural areas were seemingly not much influenced by consumer cultures. In a survey, it was found that most working women were engaged in varied employment, especially involving low wages in urban areas were not able to create any real wealth and a sizeable part of their income was usually spent for their minimum subsistence (Kumar, P & Chandok. J, 2008). The same could be true for male workers engaged in casual or low wage employment in urban areas. Nevertheless, at the same time the survey also revealed that male or women engaged in casual or low wage employment unable to create any substantial savings that might go for investments or promotion of livelihood and household in urban areas. Even in case of employment involving relatively higher income, it's not possible for both male and female workers in urban areas to use their earnings other than fulfilling their minimum subsistence. It's apparent that because of low salary or inadequate remuneration and packages they were not in a position to even dream more about better housing, secure investments and enduring their savings. However, at the same time the survey also said that women in academic professions, especially in the government sector, doctors, professors, administrative positions, and lawyers able to invest in infrastructure and other means of gainful production even in urban areas. According to the survey the situation for rural working women was quite different as most of the women in rural areas were having different 'money use' pattern due to their attitude, requirements and lack of consumer culture in comparison of their urban counterpart.

Yet another survey found that woman in rural areas had utilized their money in the most precise manner and improved their savings (Gupta, M 2009). It is appeared justified under the premises of the fact that rural areas of India not so influenced by consumer culture. It's further evident that in rural areas women were better positioned to utilize their income for the wellbeing of their respective families, especially in education, managing nutrition and health care for children. They were able to contribute significantly to their respective agriculture, dairy, poultry, group forestry or mix farming. Certainly, the women workforce in the rural areas were able to use their income in a more defined manner in comparison of women in the urban areas.

The methodology:

The overall study was conducted mainly using qualitative research methods whereby case studies, interviews, and sample surveys performed in different states of the country during the year 2009-2011. The amount of case study and interviews performed mentioned in **Table-1** and **Table-2**; therefore please see in **Table-1** and **Table-2**. A survey was also conducted among 200 NRHM women workers

belonging to different like Bihar, Jharkhand, West Bengal, and Uttar Pradesh.

E-mail surveys also conducted whereby leading official in charge of implementing NRHM in different states contacted through E-mails and invited to participate in the survey. The survey questionnaire sent to almost 124 such officials and their answer recorded. Reminders also sent in certain cases. Almost 89 officials responded and out of which 62 responses usable.

The research accomplished in stages. In initial stage, estimation of the number of women engaged under NRHM done based on 'RHS 2008' bulletin and 'MIS on NRHM for the Year March 2010. 'RHS or Rural Health Survey' was yearly survey done by the Government of India provide information about infrastructure, workforce and logistics available for the rural health sector in the country. 'MIS on NRHM' was compiled data on the performance of NRHM for the different states of the country. 'MIS on NRHM' also contained status on workforce, infrastructure, and different programs.

In second stage estimation of income of women engaged under NRHM. This done because of salary structure of different posts that found varying from state to state.

The case studies have found that several women employed under NRHM were also engaged in any alternative livelihoods. The income of women engaged under another form of livelihood estimated because of survey performed on women. The sample survey performed on 204 women engaged under NRHM belonging to different states such as Bihar, Jharkhand, West Bengal, and Uttar Pradesh. The study was conducted during 2012 took into account a period of 2005-12.

Results:

The numerical adequacy of woman under NRHM:

Women were engaged in large numbers under NRHM and could be described as 'numerical adequacy' or "statistical control" in those contexts. The total number of women engaged under NRHM surpassed male many folds. Their number expected to further increase as all vacant posts filled in coming years. Numerical adequacy of women work force under NRHM mostly due the fact out of almost 82 kind of work force required and women could engage in any kind of open as NRHM a more gender friendly besides their certain posts where only women could get employment. Such post mentioned in tabular form in **Table-5** and their required number mentioned. Women found largely engaged as *Auxiliary Nurse and Midwives (ANMs)*, *Aanganwadi Workers (AWWs)*, *Accredited Social Health Activists (ASHAs)*, *Lady Health Visitor (LHVs)*, *Lady Medical doctors* and women in different managerial, supervisory, or administrative positions (MOHFW 2006). It's estimated that more than two million women engaged in the country in the rural health sector under NRHM alone and thus it the greatest ever-reported women work force in the country in a

single public sector. Such numerical adequacy could not for mere showpiece, but definitely created opportunities for women to cross the barriers of the culture, custom, and traditions to strengthen and prove their natural leadership qualities and abilities outside their respective households. Under NRHM, they could involve with the entire gamut of immunization, institutional delivery, and nutritional activities. The moment this numerical adequacy mixed with spillover effects the total count would be impressive.

Accredited Social Health Activists (ASHAs):

ASHAs supposed to appoint in each village having a population of one thousand at least. Any woman married in that particular village could select as 'ASHA'. An especial committee set up in each village panchayat to select ASHA. So far, nearly 0.9 million ASHAs selected in the country. They required five stages of training and equipped with drug kits under the NRHM. They truly become the flag bearers of NRHM in the country. In the form of ASHA, a new cadre of women work force introduced in between the existing cadres of ANMs and AWWs. This done to ease the work of ANMs who used to remain overburdened most of the times. ASHAs sometimes could refer as *Sahiya* and *Mitani* in Jharkhand and Chhattisgarh states respectively.

The core responsibility of ASHA was to assist respective ANMs and AWWs in routine immunization, institutional delivery, nutritional care, etc. They expected to record the new pregnancy occurring in their territory and report urgently. However, ASHAs could not claim to be an employee of the government and were not eligible for any fixed salary or scale but certain provisions existed for performance-based incentives. The regulation of the ASHA scheme in the country would be a matter of great interest in future as how it would turn around in the future was a matter of great interest for development practitioners. Despite all contradictions, their role acquired extremely significance not only in the field of health but in certain spillover, an effect also felt in the other socioeconomic areas.

Aanganwadi workers (AWWs):

AWWs introduced in the country under the scheme of ICDS (Integrated Child Development Scheme) and responsible for nutrition of women and child in their respective geographical areas. After convergence, their role became important under the NRHM. It's estimated that nearly 0.9 million AWWs recruited and working in the country to date.

Auxiliary Nurse and Midwives (ANMs):

It's expected that there would be at least one ANM per health sub centre covering a population of five thousand in the country in plain areas and three thousand population in hilly or hard to reach areas. However, Indian Public Health Standards in its revised draft format 2010 recommended two ANMs per Sub Centers. Each Health Sub Center required covered by one ANM, which further expected doubling in due course of time. So far almost 0.2 million

ANMs engaged and working in the country under NRHM. This number would increase further the moment more health sub centers would come into being according to population norms of the Indian Public Health Standards and each sub centers would have at least two ANMs.

The main roles of ANMs were to accomplish Reproductive and Child Health activities, especially routine immunization and provide services under different national disease control programs as suggested by the Indian Public Health Standards. They mostly worked as the first contact point for health services at the village level.

Lady health visitors (LHVs):

It's estimated that at least sixty thousand LHVs were working in the country under NRHM. The responsibilities of a LHV were to supervise and coordinate immunization and other health programs in a given geographical area. She expected to work in Co relation of medical officers of the Primary Health Centre on the side and ANMs, AWWs and ASHAs on the other sides.

Lady medical doctors:

It was required to ensure the availability of at least one-lady doctors in each primary health centre of the country. It's estimated that there were more than 10 thousand woman doctors engaged under NRHM. This number expected to increase further as no vacant posts were filled and new health facilities also expected to come up. This number was despite the fact that woman doctor was not provided to each Primary Health Centre in the country due to tremendous scarcity of doctors.

Women in managerial and administrative positions:

It's never the case that women under NRHM were largely engaged in facilitating peripheral services, but they also deployed in substantial numbers in managerial and supervisory positions such as part of a program management unit, program Officers, and consultants. Unlike ASHA, AWW and ANM which expected to deliver peripheral services they were responsible for collecting, processing and presenting reports, performing analysis and preparing plans of action at district, state or central levels.

The Income of women engaged under NRHM:

The income level of women under NRHM mentioned in Tabular form in **Table-4**; therefore please see in **Table-4**. Most of the recruitments under NRHM could base on contractual agreements between the employee and government. Women under NRHM not provided any pay scale other than a fixed salary, which provided to them mostly on monthly basis. It noted that salary also differed from state to state.

It would be evident that most of the women engaged under NRHM as ASHA, AWW and ANM were having diminutive income and with such kind of income, it was not possible for them to manage their basic requirements for minimum

subsistence beyond subsistence. Therefore, in most cases it found that women being not fully satisfied with their income had engaged themselves in another form of livelihood mainly dairy, poultry, and horticulture. They started a small dairy involving cows and buffalos. Some started a small poultry involving production of eggs and chicken and some started growing fruits and vegetables for both domestic and commercial purposes. Weaving, tailoring, and stitching some other jobs, they also found engaged. Such extra livelihood could only possible in rural areas and one of the main highlights of the NRHM that it created large-scale employment for woman in rural areas.

The survey:

Out of 200 women, 39 women said that they were not satisfied with the salary what they get under NRHM, as that was not enough for even their basic requirements, thus they made a decision to involve in other form of livelihood after completing their duties. A quite remarkable response that almost 20 per cent women engaged in the capacity of ANM, ASHA and AWW made to think about alternative form of livelihood. Most of them also said that primarily they were enthused by their engagement under NRHM, which provided them a basis to engage in another form of livelihood. In almost 79 percent cases, it noticed that though alternative livelihood started by women workers, but they managed by their unemployed husbands or sons and unmarried daughters.

Discussion:

In fact, it became evident that though the mandate of NRHM not directly or visibly said anything about women empowerment despite it could say that NRHM benefitted women on massive scale both directly and indirectly. Direct benefits could in the manner of paving way for large-scale employment for women and the successful implementation of NRHM further benefitted women indirectly. Reduction in Infant Mortality Rate, Maternal Mortality Rate, Burden of Diseases and marked increase in coverage of immunization, ambulatory, referral and OPD/IPD services also benefitted women indirectly. It reduced their dependence on male members of the households for several key issues.

The effect of NRHM was relatively more perceptible in the rural parts of the country. Being the leader of the household, women could natural beneficiary of any positive makeover of the health services. India, a country, almost 62 children used to die each year out of every one thousand children and almost 340 women used to die each year out of every 0.1 million pregnant women till the year 2005. After the successful execution of NRHM over the last five years, these figures now stood at 50 and 250 respectively in the year 2010. The sex ration in India was almost 941 women per 1000 men improved after execution of NRHM. In fact, in some states number of females already surpassed males. NRHM also took care of nutrition of women and child. We must know that sizeable part of Indian women used to suffer from anemia or abnormal body mass index.

One of the main highlights of the NRHM could be also that women benefitted without any explicit arrangements. Issues related to women empowerment, gender justice or gender equality acquired significance and several developmental programs showed genuine concern on such issues. Nevertheless, it could say with certainty that Women Empowerment, Gender, Justice, and Equality never central to the idea of planning for a program like NRHM because health programs more focused and visible. Therefore, at first glance, many social scientists and development practitioner used to see NRHM more as a health program, however, with such findings I could also term NRHM as one of the most successful developmental programs in the country since independence. Therefore, it was quite unwise to think that gender empowerment, not any issue under NRHM nevertheless, such issues emerging out stronger definitely surprised many social scientists. Such issues more observed, studied in coming days as more and more reports would emerge out.

Under NRHM, the numerical adequacy for women established without any special arrangements. It could a realization of the emotions, commitments, and concern that any woman usually used to possess. It would definitely become a most distinguished milestone in the efforts of establishing gender justice and equality in the country.

It would be also important to mention that working environment under NRHM in rural areas never easy. ANMs, AWWs, ASHAs, LHVs required to perform in difficult terrain and hard to reach areas. In addition, on several instances serious discrepancies existed in terms of work condition, supportive mechanism, and supply of logistics. Despite this fact, the contribution of woman could term laudable because they created a platform for the public health sector in the country to take off. NRHM succeeded supplementary in those sectors where more women involved, especially in the field of immunization, OPD/IPD, nutrition, pulse polio, disease control, and ensuring institutional delivery.

It could be noted that rural working woman in India found having specific '*time - money use pattern*'. They proved to be more efficient in managing their time for a varied kind of labor like household, livelihood and employment related labor. Woman under NRHM were able to manage all three forms of labor in order to increase their income and well-being of respective households. Similarly, rural woman were also able to manage their money in the most ethical manner which not only promoted their savings, but they became enabled in investing their savings in other productive activities such as dairy, poultry, agriculture, knitting-weaving and sale- supply of consumer goods on part time basis. They became able to perform such varied activities mainly due to distinct money wise and time use patterns of rural woman in India and therefore this was the most crucial aspect of this paper.

Women workers were engaged in mission of population control, reduction of the burden of diseases virtually contributed greatly to the nation building. No surprise that role of women could was quite significantly in increasing coverage of immunization which resulted in protection of infants from certain diseases also by promoting the institutional delivery, marked decline in maternal mortality rate and infant mortality rate observed. With better nutritional care, it became ultimately possible for women and children at the micro level to expect a healthy lifestyle and longer life expectancy. Women and children were having reasons to feel some sense of security against illness and burden of diseases in the rural areas due to a rapid increase of various public health services. This further helped women and children in most specific and sustained manner. Burden of diseases used to cripple households massively therefore decline in burden of diseases consecutively contributed rural household and livelihood in most sustained manner.

With the reduction in burden of diseases and increased sense of security against illness, the economy of the family or household witnessed the tremendous solidarity. I came across with real experience that how some ANMs and ASHAs and AWWs able to invest in small dairy, agriculture and vegetation activities even though in a limited manner. Some purchased one–two cows or buffalos, not only provided any additional income, but at the same time, they substantially nourished the family. At some places, they invested in agriculture and started producing vegetables for both personal use and sale purposes. In most cases sanitation and hygiene, level of education of the children also improved.

Therefore, it could say that women workforce engaged in large numbers under NRHM in rural areas resulted in better management of not only respective household, but their other livelihood such as dairy, poultry and agriculture also. The success of NRHM also benefitted other socioeconomic sector and the spillover effect evident. NRHM termed quite successful in creating large-scale awareness on several issues such as sanitation, hygiene, nutrition and gender issues involving development. NRHM also promoted women's activism in the society largely. The increased women's activism naturally strengthened position of the respective women in order to promote other developmental activities such as self-help groups, microfinance, skill development, and employment programs at the micro level.

Conclusions:

Women empowerment was not directly any agenda under NRHM but the successful implementation of NRHM benefitted women in varied manner. It was evident that immunization coverage, OPD/IPD services, Ambulatory Services, Nutritional services, and Institutional delivery registered phenomenal growth in the country and in these sectors women massively engaged. NRHM has benefitted women in three angles firstly it created and provided

employment opportunity for woman on a large scale in rural areas. Secondly, women grabbed well those opportunities to prove their indispensability and executed their work most precisely, which helped the successful implementation of NRHM in several key areas. Due to the successful implementation of the health program burden of diseases index declined and it benefitted women indirectly. Thirdly, women utilized their natural skill to manage time and money most precisely to create some alternative livelihood.

Several spillover effects of successful implementation of NRHM were also evident in the country. The success achieved in the field of primary health care had created a conducive situation for other developmental programs to succeed. Similar replica could achieve in other developmental programs such as ‘Sarva Shikha Abhiyan (SSA)’ and ‘Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Program’ (MNREGA). The added income to the family in rural areas also went for better management of soil, water, and agriculture. The awareness about nutrition, sanitation, health issues, and hygiene also improved drastically. Women employed under NRHM were also able to manage better education for their children.

Key messages:

The achievements of women under NRHM would also contradict the overall idea of women empowerment through special arrangements or favored policies. In fact, under NRHM women performed without any favored policies. NRHM could serve as an instance in this regard.

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Conflict of interest:

None

Tables:

Table-1: Amount of case studies.

Name of places	Focus of case study	Case Programs
24 Health sub centres	Building, Logistics, Manpower. Registers, records.	Immunization, JSY, Sanitation, Nutrition.
15 Primary health centres Hussainabad, Chattarpur, Manika, Balumath, Garu, Brawadih and Panki	Building, Logistics, Manpower, Lady doctor, Ambulance, OPD/IPD,	Immunization, JSY, Sanitation, Nutrition, National Health Programs,

in Jharkhand, Dhanarua, Ghosi and Barh in Bihar,	Laboratory, Cold Chain, Operation theatre, RKS Registers, records.	Survey and data collection, Health camps, Flow of reports
5 Community health centres Ranka and Mahudand in Jharkhand, Masurhi , Barh and Arwal in Bihar,	Building, Logistics, Manpower, Lady doctor, Ambulance, OPD/IPD, Laboratory, Cold Chain, Operation theatre, RKS, Registers, records.	Immunization, JSY, Sanitation, Nutrition, National Health Programs, Flow of reports and funds..
12 District Hospitals Patna, Begusarai, Muzaffarpur in Bihar. Ranchi, Plamau, Garhwa and latehar in Jharkhand. Gorakhpur and Meerut in UP. Bikaner in Rajasthan, Chamoli in Uttarakhand, Bankura in West Bengal, Cuttack in Orissa, Raipur in Chattisgarh.	Building, Logistics, Manpower, Specialists, Ambulance, OPD/IPD, Laboratory, Cold Chain, Diagnostics services, Blood Storage, IMNCI, Immunization, Sterilization, RKS, Level of training, Hygiene, Registers, records.	Immunization, JSY, Sanitation, Nutrition, National Health Programs, PPP, Outsourcing. Flow of reports and funds.
5 State health societies of Bihar, Jharkhand, West Bengal, UP, Rajasthan and Uttarakhand.	Status of manpower in state, HR and Accounts management, Number of meetings, Training,	Innovative arrangements, National health programs, PPP, Outsourcing, Establishment of medical or paramedical institutions.

Table-2: The amount of interviews performed.

S. No.	Case	Interviews
1	At Village level	Total Number of Interviews: 77 Sarpanchs:12 AWWs:20 ASHAs:24 General Public:21
2	At Health Sub Centre level	Total Number of

		Interviews: 135 ANMs:135
3	At primary Health Centre level	Total Number of Interviews: 72 MOICs:25 Doctors:13 LHVs:22 PMU:12
4	At community health centre level	Total Number of Interviews: 29 MOICs:11 Doctors:18
5	At District level	Total Number of Interviews: 71 CMOs:8 Dy. CMOs:09 Doctors:18 DMs/DCs:14 MLAs:6 NGOs:9 PMU team: 7
6	At state level	Total Number of Interviews: 6 Mission Director:1 SPMU Team: 5

Total interviews: 390.

Table-3: Estimated number of women work force in public health sector in India

S. No.	Name of post	Estimated number
1.	Accredited social health activists	900000
2.	Aanganwadi workers	800000
3.	Auxiliary nurse and midwives	200000
4.	Lady health visitors	4500
5.	Ladies trainers	2300
6.	Supervisors	4500
7.	Managers	3500
8.	Consultants	1400
9.	Office assistants	5600
10.	Lady doctors	12500
11.	Program officers	550
12.	Administrative positions	450

Sources: RHS bulletins 2008

Table-4: The level of salary under NRHM to women workforce

S. No.	Name of post	Monthly salary/incentives in rupees
1.	Accredited social health activists	2000-4000
2.	Aanganwadi workers	4000-8000
3.	Auxiliary nurse and midwives	8000-16000
4.	Lady health visitors	10000-20000
5.	Teachers/ trainers	20000-30000
6.	Supervisors	20000-25000
7.	Managers	30000-50000

8.	Consultants	30000-50000
9.	Office assistants	5000-20000
10.	Lady doctors	20000-40000
11.	Program officers	30000-50000
12.	Administrative positions	40000-60000

Source: Sample surveys conducted by the author.

Table-5: Jobs specifically for women

S.No.	Workforce	Required
1	Obstetrician & Gynecologist	22188
2	Lady Health Visitor	31457
3	Public health nurse	10082
4	Nurse	407440
5	Sister in charge	12100
6	General duty workers/ hospital attendants	50840
7	ANM	488888
8	Health workers females	282354
9	Health assistants females	80664
10	Matron	3631
11	Assistant matron	1211
12	Aya	50410

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